

ROEL JENNISSEN* - LEO VAN WISSEN**

The distribution of asylum seekers over Northern and Western European countries, 1985-2005

1. INTRODUCTION AND OUTLINE

In the 1980s increasing numbers of asylum seekers sought refuge in mainly Northern and Western Europe. Similar to other types of migration, asylum migration may exert a considerable impact on social and political life in receiving countries. Asylum migration is often more multifaceted than migration types such as colonial, labour, family and retirement migration. In general asylum flows contain a larger diversity of nationalities and age groups. In this article we try to identify factors that influence this multifarious migration type in potential receiving countries in Europe. A distinction has been made between social, institutional (including legal) and economic factors. The volume of asylum migration is, at least for a considerable part, determined by factors in the region of origin – a sincere asylum migrant has only push motives underlying his decision to migrate. Nevertheless, the choice of a certain country of destination can undoubtedly partly be determined by factors in potential receiving countries. Hence, the aim of this article is to identify factors that influence the distribution of asylum seekers in Europe.

The research has been limited to Northern and Western European countries in the period from 1985 to 2005. Altogether, 12 Northern and Western European countries have been included in the study¹. Eastern European countries have not been included in the analysis as many asylum seekers who apply for asylum in these countries are actually aiming to travel to Western Europe and do so when they get the opportunity (Van Dam and Van der Erf, 1998). Southern European countries have not been taken into account, as potential asylum migrants who intended to enter these countries preferred clandestine sojourn rather than the regular asylum procedure. The extensive hidden economy in Southern Europe provided fair job opportunities for clandestines (see e.g. Reyneri, 2001). Furthermore, Southern European governments regularly confer legal status to clandestines who stay in the country for a long time. The decision to apply for asylum in one of the northern or western countries, or to seek clandestine refuge in one of the southern countries is real and an interest-

* Netherlands Ministry of Security and Justice - WODC, Den Haag, Netherlands.

** Netherlands Interdisciplinary Demographic Institute (NIDI), Den Haag, Netherlands
Corresponding author: Roel Jennissen, email: r.p.w.jennissen@minvenj.nl

¹ All Western and Northern European countries with a population of more than one million have been taken into account. These countries are Austria, Belgium, Denmark, France, Finland, (West) Germany, the Irish Republic, the Netherlands, Norway, Sweden, Switzerland and the UK.

ing one. Unfortunately, we have no information (except the information about the regularisation programmes, see e.g. Cangiano, 2008) about undocumented migration to southern countries.

This research has been limited to the period up to 2005 as the division of Europe into three different migration systems (asylum migration in Northern and Western Europe, transit migration in Eastern Europe and illegal sojourn in Southern Europe) with respect to potential asylum seekers does not hold true from that time anymore. Two phenomena significantly changed this situation. Firstly, eight Eastern European countries became EU member states. This implies that transit migration from these countries to Western Europe became more difficult as the EU membership of these countries entailed that these countries also became subscribers of the Dublin Regulation. This regulation determines that the EU member state where an asylum seeker sets foot on EU territory for the first time is responsible for the treatment of the asylum request of this asylum seeker (Chotkowski *et al.*, 2014). Secondly, the financial crisis that existed in 2007 and in 2010 changed from a banking crisis into a public debt crisis had a relatively large negative impact on the economy of the Southern European countries. The financial-economic crisis will probably also have a negative impact on the job opportunities in the hidden economy of the Southern European countries in which many illegal migrants have found employee (see e.g. Maroukis, 2013). Hence, it is far from inconceivable that the position of Southern Europe in the European asylum system will gradually change from an alternative in the form of illegal labour migration for asylum migration in Northern and Western Europe to the position of a transit area (comparable to Eastern Europe). Triandafyllidou and Maroukis (2012) found indications that the situation is indeed heading in that direction.

In order to provide a background of the phenomenon of asylum migration in Europe, section 2 describes the course of a displaced person who chooses to become an asylum migrant in Europe. Section 3 focuses on asylum applications in Northern and Western Europe in the period 1985-2005. Moreover, factors which influence the distribution of asylum seekers over the Northern and Western Europe countries will be described on the basis of actual asylum flows. Section 4 is the analytical part of this article. This section contains a description of the factors determining the choice of a country of asylum (section 4.1) and the data used (section 4.2). Analyses will be conducted on the distribution of the total number of asylum applications (section 4.3) and of asylum applications from (the former) Yugoslavia (section 4.4). Finally, section 5 provides some conclusions and a discussion.

2. BACKGROUND: BECOMING AN ASYLUM MIGRANT IN EUROPE

The course of a displaced person who becomes an asylum migrant in Europe is rather long. This course, in which a potential asylum migrant (or traf-

ficker) has to make a number of choices and finally undergoes a screening by the authorities in the receiving country, is illustrated in Figure 1. The question that arises is whether we may speak about a choice here. Often displaced persons have no or a limited choice because of limited (financial) means or other restrictive circumstances.

The first "choice" is whether to leave home and become a displaced person or not. People have different reasons to flee from their country of residence. Zolberg *et al.* (1989) distinguish three categories of refugees: the refugee as an activist, as a target and as a victim. Refugees who are activists have been involved in some political action against the authorities of their country of residence. Those who are targets are members of a social or cultural group on whom violence is perpetrated by the state or other social or cultural groups. Refugees who are victims are exposed to societal or international-level violence in their country of residence. However, this violence is not directed at them as individuals. It is, however, difficult to make a strict distinction between the three aforementioned categories of refugees. For instance, people who stand up for the rights of a social or cultural minority are often also members of this social or cultural minority. It may also be difficult to disentangle migration motivated by material gain and migration motivated by fear of violence as countries with political chaos and violence are often countries with a low GDP per capita, high unemployment and a low level of social security (United Nations, 1997). Moreover, a policy to undermine the economic position of a cultural or social minority may be part of a general policy to discriminate or persecute a particular cultural or social section of the population (Zolberg *et al.*, 1989).

Once on the move, the question is where to seek refuge. By far most refugees that flee from their own country seek protection in the surrounding countries. Only a relatively small proportion seeks asylum in other parts of the world (Europe, North America or Oceania). Europe received refugees from its own backyard (e.g. Yugoslavia, Turkey, North Caucasus and Transcaucasia) as well as from other parts of the world. North America and Oceania only received refugees from other continents. However, we may observe a regional component in the refugee flows to these two continents as well; many Central American and Caribbean refugees sought asylum in North America, whereas a relatively large number of refugees from South-east Asia sought asylum in Oceania. African and Asia countries almost solely received refugees from their own neighbours on the same continent. The framework presented in Figure 1 depicts this problem as a set of subsequent choices, where each ensuing choice leads to a more distant destination: resettlement in one's own country, in neighbouring countries or overseas.

Figure 1 – *The course taken by a displaced person to become an asylum migrant in Northern or Western Europe until the extension of the EU in 2004*

Notes:

ⁱ *Surrounding* countries may also be situated in Europe (e.g. for refugees from the former Yugoslavia).

ⁱⁱ The European Union before the enlargement of May 2004.

Europe is one of the overseas destinations, except for refugees from the former Yugoslavia, which has the European Union as its neighbour. Within Europe the Northern and Western part of the continent are, by far, the most important destination regions. Refugees who seek refuge in Northern and Western Europe have to choose a particular country of asylum in this region. A considerable proportion of the asylum seekers does not consciously choose a particular country of asylum. Often a trafficker or the presence of a mainport (i.e. an intercontinental airport) determines the “choice” of a particular country. Most asylum seekers use the services of traffickers or human smugglers at least one stage of their journey (Monheim, 2008). Many people have a picture in their mind of traffickers as reckless criminals who do not care about the individuals they move. However, this view is only partly correct. Potential refugees often know the reputation of a trafficker and only take their chance with a reliable one. Therefore, traffickers are concerned with their reputation, which is made or blasted by the persons who were trafficked in the past (Monheim, 2008). Thus, we may state that the “choices” that traffickers make are to a certain extent similar to those that an individual refugee would make. The next section focuses on trends in the number of asylum seekers in Northern and Western European countries in from the 1980s until 2005.

3. ASYLUM SEEKERS IN NORTHERN AND WESTERN EUROPE

Most asylum seekers that sought refuge in Europe in the first half of the 1980s originated from Asia, followed by (Eastern) Europe and Africa. Asylum migration from Asia peaked in the middle of the 1980s. Armed conflicts in Sri Lanka, Afghanistan and Lebanon and the war between Iran and Iraq caused a large flow of refugees. In addition, many Indians, Pakistani and Vietnamese applied for asylum in Europe. European inflow of asylum seekers peaked in 1981 (almost 50,000 applications). In that year Austria received 34,500 mainly Polish asylum seekers (Te Brake, 1993). The distribution of asylum seekers over the European countries was rather disproportionate. In Europe, West Germany had by far the biggest inflow of asylum seekers in the 1980s (Eurostat, 1997). Sweden, France and Austria also received a considerable proportion of the asylum seekers who sought refuge in Europe in the 1980s. Sweden, Switzerland, Germany and Austria were the leading countries in terms of number of asylum applications per head of the total population (UNHCR, 1998). All the aforementioned countries are among the most prosperous countries in Europe. This may be an indication that economic factors (i.e. GDP per capita or opportunities on the labour market) have a positive

¹ As we illustrate in the following Section 3, the standard geographical categorization of Italian regions among North, Centre and South and urban dimensions can be efficiently used as a proxy of the persistent cultural and normative differences.

effect on the number of asylum applications. Next to economic factors, asylum policies (legislation) may determine the choice of a particular country of asylum. Compared to other countries, West Germany had a lenient asylum legislation (Fijalkovski, 1993; Kurthen, 1995; Wendt, 1997). The stocks of already present migrants also play a significant role in the distribution of asylum seekers. These stocks, in which migrants networks may be formed, are not necessarily the result of earlier asylum flows. They can also be caused by former labour or (post)colonial migration flows (Castles and Loughna, 2003). An example of a migrant stock arising from labour migration which served as a network for asylum migrants is the Turkish community in Germany. Political turmoil in Turkey, ending with a military coup d'état in 1980, caused a large flow of asylum seekers and family migration from Turkey to Germany in the late 1970s and 1980 (Muus and Van Dam, 1998). Havinga and Böcker (1999) state that the colonial past accounts for the relatively high number of Africans in France, the UK, Portugal and Belgium, the relatively high number of Asians in France and the relatively high number of Latin Americans in Spain.

In the second half of the 1980s less restrictive emigration policies caused increasing (asylum) emigration from European communist countries. As a result asylum migration in Western Europe was given an additional dimension. Originally, asylum migration mainly involved south-to-north migration, but by the late 1980s asylum migration also included east-to-west migration. West German immigration figures substantially increased in the second half of the 1980s. This rising number of immigrants was due to an increasing inflow of asylum seekers and *Aussiedler* from Central and Eastern Europe. By the end of the 1980s communism collapsed in Eastern Europe. The period 1989-92 was very turbulent. The war in the former Yugoslavia and the unstable situation in the former Soviet Union caused a large inflow of European asylum seekers. Meanwhile, an ongoing flow of refugees from Asia and Africa sought asylum in Western Europe. In the period 1988-92 Germany still received the most asylum applications in Northern and Western Europe (51.8 per cent) followed by France (10.6 per cent) and Sweden (8.9 per cent). Similar to the 1980s Sweden, Switzerland and Germany were the leading countries in Europe in this period in terms of asylum applications vis-à-vis national population.

In the mid-1990s asylum applications in Northern and Western Europe did not reach the level of the previous period (see Figure 2). The main causes of this decrease were stricter asylum policies and the end of the war in Bosnia-Herzegovina (Van Selm-Thornburn, 1998; OECD, 1998). The crisis in Kosovo caused a renewed increase in the number of asylum seekers from Europe at the end of the 1990s. Meanwhile, the number of African and Asian refugees who lodged an asylum application in also rose gradually. This last-

ed until 2003. Declining numbers of asylum seekers from Africa and Asia, together with an ongoing decrease in the number of refugees from the own continent, led to a significant decrease in the number of asylum applications in Northern and Western Europe after 2002.

Figure 2 – *Total number of asylum applications in Northern and Western Europe by continent of origin*

Source: 1985-1999: Eurostat; Sources 2000-2005: OFPRA, National Statistics and Eurostat.

Note: 1985-1999: no data for the Irish Republic 1985 and 1986. The data for the continents for Austria 1995 and 1997-99, Belgium 1985-87, 1994-95 and 1998, Denmark 1999, France 1999, Finland 1985-89 and 1999, Germany 1994-95 (and 1996 for Latin America), Norway 1994-98, Sweden 1995-96 and Switzerland 1993-96 have been estimated with the distribution of totals between the continents based on the (average) distribution of the proximate available year(s). 2000-2005: Own estimations for the continents of origin based on the distribution in France, Germany and the UK.

The number of asylum applications in a certain country may not only be influenced by the migration policy of the country itself, but also by the migration policy of the neighbouring countries. In the Netherlands, for instance, the number of new asylum requests rose from about 35,000 in 1993 to about 53,000 in 1994, while the total number of asylum requests in Europe declined (see Figure 3). The number of new requests in the Netherlands reached a peak in 1994. This peak was probably caused by stricter asylum policies in the neighbouring countries (especially in Germany) (Van Wissen and De Beer, 2000). Another possible explanation for this peak was the increasing inflow

of Somali asylum seekers. In 1995 and 1996 the number of new requests decreased again to about the level of 1992. This decrease was caused by stricter conditions relating to application for asylum in 1994 and by the Dayton Peace Treaty (Nicolaas, 1997). Germany (54.1 per cent), the UK (8.7 per cent) and the Netherlands (8.5 per cent) were the most important destination countries for asylum migrants in Northern and Western Europe in the period 1992-1999, while the UK (20.7 per cent), Germany (18.9 per cent) and France (15.1 per cent) were the most important destination countries in the first years of the new millennium (until 2006).

Figure 3 – *Asylum applications in selected Northern and Western European countries, 1985-2005*

Source: Eurostat.

Figure 4 depicts the number of asylum applications per 1000 inhabitants in four selected Northern and Western European countries. The very large peak in Sweden in 1992 is remarkable. In that year Sweden received almost one asylum application per 100 inhabitants. Asylum seekers from the former Yugoslavia accounted for the major part (83 per cent) of the asylum applications in 1992 (ICMPD, 1994). Furthermore, figure 4 shows that asylum seekers “discovered” the Irish Republic as a potential destination country in the second half of the 1990s. Strong economic growth is probably a significant reason why the Irish Republic has become a more important destination country for asylum seekers.

Figure 4 – *Asylum applications per 1000 inhabitants in selected Northern and Western European countries*

Source: Eurostat.

4. MULTIVARIATE MODELS

In this section we present models to explain the distribution of asylum applications over Northern and Western European countries. In particular, we focus on the distribution of the total amount of asylum applications and asylum applications from the former Yugoslavia.

4.1 *Factors that may have an impact on the choice of a country of asylum*

Figure 5 can be seen as a close-up of figure 1, which zooms in on the lowest three rectangles, from ‘Northern and Western Europe’ to ‘refugee recognition’. It reflects a systematic overview of the factors that may have an impact on a potential applicant’s choice of a certain European country of asylum. These factors are divided into economic, network, legislative and institutional factors.

Economic variables (for instance GDP per capita and unemployment) may influence the choice of a country of asylum, because these variables are fairly good predictors of income (GDP per capita) or the likelihood of a job (unemployment) once a refugee status is granted. Moreover, it is likely that countries with a high level of economic prosperity (i.e. high GDP per

capita) offer asylum seekers better facilities during their asylum procedures. Economic factors may also influence the choice of a country of asylum indirectly. Labour market developments in potential receiving countries can have an effect on the attitude towards asylum seekers. In times of large scale unemployment for instance, immigrants (e.g. refugees with a status) are often considered competitors on the labour market by the public opinion. In times of labour shortages on the other hand, immigrants are often seen as the solution to this problem. The attitude towards immigrants may have an impact on asylum policies, which in turn may affect the distribution of asylum seekers over European countries. GDP per capita and unemployment are the variables which have been used in the analyses to represent prosperity effects that might have impact on the distribution of asylum seekers over the countries in Northern and Western Europe. GDP per capita is presumed to exert a positive effect and unemployment a negative effect on the share of a particular country in the total number of asylum seekers in Northern and Western Europe. Previous quantitative studies on the distribution of asylum seekers in Europe of Thielemann (2003) and Neumayer (2004) established these effects of GDP per capita and unemployment, respectively.

Figure 5 – *Factors that may have an impact on the choice of a country of asylum*

It is quite obvious that asylum policies have an effect on the share of a particular country in the total number of asylum applications submitted in Northern and Western Europe (see e.g. Hatton, 2004). Moreover, as we already saw in section 3, this share may be determined by immigration policies in surrounding countries as well. In order to take into account important policy measures in the country itself and in surrounding countries, some policy dummy variables have been used in the models (see table 2).

The migrant stock has been used in the analyses to represent the influence of migrant networks and institutional factors. As a result of large inflows of international migrants, migrant networks may be formed, involving interpersonal linkages between (migrant) populations in origin and destination areas. Migrant networks may help potential migrants of the same ethnic origin, for instance, by contributing to financing the journey, helping to find a job or appropriate accommodation, or by giving information about education possibilities or access to social security (Esveldt et al., 1995). As international migration occurs on a large scale it can become institutionalised. According to institutional theory, a large inflow of international migrants induces profit and non-profit organisations, which can be legal or illegal, to provide, for instance, (clandestine) transport, labour contracts, (counterfeit) documents, dwellings or legal advice for migrants (Massey et al., 1993). We presume that the migrant stock has a positive effect on the share of a particular country in the total number of asylum seekers in Northern and Western Europe. Thielemann (2003) already found a positive effect of the migrant stock in earlier research.

We referred to three studies in the previous paragraphs (Thielemann, 2003; Hatton, 2004; Neumayer, 2004). As far as we know, these are the only macro-level empirical studies on the determinants of the distribution of asylum seekers over European countries. Our research distinguishes itself in two aspects from this previous pioneering work. First, we focus on the Northern and Western European countries and leave the countries in Southern Europe (Greece, Italy, Portugal and Spain) out of consideration. We think that the inclusion of these countries in which potential asylum migrants prefer clandestine sojourn rather than the regular asylum procedure and have, therefore, relatively low figures of asylum seekers may distort the results. It is not inconceivable that a relationship exists between the number of asylum seekers in (Northern and Western) Europe and the number of irregular migrants entering the (Southern) European countries. Our focus on Northern and Western Europe neutralises this disturbing factor. Secondly, we use a conditional logit model (see the next section) instead of (log-)linear regression analysis with the per capita share of asylum seekers as dependent variable.

4.2 *Data² and methodology*

The dependent variable in the analyses in this study is derived from the number of asylum applications (source: Eurostat³). We have to be aware of three rather confounding data issues when conducting research into asylum applications. First, pre-selection may be a serious problem. Some countries may have a stricter admittance policy than others. Second, we have to deal with the problem of double counts in the case of lodging an appeal. Finally, some countries only register the main applicant and ignore their children. These confounding data issues may affect the results of our analyses.

We use conditional logit models to explain the dispersion of asylum applications over Northern and Western European countries. A conditional logit model, which is frequently applied in migration research, is expressed as follows:

$$\Pr ob(Y_t = i) = Y_{it}^* = \frac{\exp(X_{it}\beta)}{\sum_{k=1}^K \exp(X_{kt}\beta)}.$$

The probability that a migrant chooses country i in year t (the proportion of country i in the total inflow in year t) is a function of the independent variables X_{it} of country i in year t . By definition $\sum_i Y_{it}^* = 1$. We use country-specific dummies α_i that capture time invariant effects of country i . Furthermore, we presume that the distribution of the migrants (in this case asylum seekers) is proportional to population Q_i of country i if we ignore other features of country i . Therefore, the model can be written as

$$\Pr ob(Y_t = i) = Y_{it}^* = \frac{Q_i \exp(\alpha_i + X_{it}\beta)}{\sum_{k=1}^K Q_k \exp(\alpha_k + X_{kt}\beta)}.$$

The independent variables that have been used in the analyses are: GDP per capita, unemployment, and the migrant stock per capita. Table 1 reflects the operationalisation and source of GDP per capita, unemployment and the migrant stock per capita.

² German data apply to West Germany for the years 1985-1989.

³ The source for the number of Yugoslavian asylum applications in Germany 1995-1996, Sweden 1995-1996 and Switzerland 1994-1996 is OECD. These data have been rounded to the nearest hundred. The source for the number of Yugoslavian asylum applications in the Netherlands 1995-1996 is Statistics Netherlands. The number of asylum seekers from the former Yugoslavia in Switzerland 2000 is an estimation based on the total number of asylum seekers.

Table 1 – *Socio-economic variables*

Variable	Operationalisation	Source
GDP per capita	1990 US\$ converted at Geary Khamis PPPs	The Conference Board
Unemployment	Total unemployment as percentage of the total labour force	EUR macro data
Migrant stock per 1000 inhabitants	Foreign nationals from sending areas ⁱ per capita ⁱⁱ	Council of Europe

Notes:

ⁱ Asia (incl. Turkey), Africa, Latin America, the former Soviet Union, the former Yugoslavia and Romania.

ⁱⁱ The number of Yugoslavian nationals per capita is used in the corresponding analysis.

The numbers of foreign nationals from areas from which asylum seekers depart are available for the years 1981, 1991 and 1999. Inter- and extra-polation using linear trends has provided complete data for the period 1985-2005⁴.

As has already been mentioned, dummy variables have been used in the models to take important policy measures into account. These variables capture the impact of observed changes in the share of asylum applications as a result of asylum policies in the country, or in other relevant European countries. Table 2 provides information about the description, the period of application and the source of these variables.

In general the implementation of immigration policies in a country may cause a structural shift towards a lower level of immigration in this particular country and possibly a shift towards a higher level of immigration in surrounding countries. However, the policy dummy variables which have been used here for the period until 1995 only affect one specific year. The reason for this is that asylum policies in Northern and Western Europe can be seen as negative policy competition to attract as few asylum seekers as possible until the end of the 1990s.

⁴ The stock in Austria 1999 = (stock 1991 x total foreign population 1999) / total foreign population 1991. The Yugoslav stock in Belgium 1999 is the average of 1998 and 2000. For France the stock in 1982 and 1990 has been used; extrapolation from 1990. Only Russian Federation data are available for the stock of former USSR nationals in France. For Germany the stock in 1980 is used. No West German data are available. For the Irish Republic the stock in 1992 is used; extrapolation before 1992. The total foreign population minus the foreign EU stock and the US stock has been used for the Irish Republic as no other data are available. The data source for nationals of the former Yugoslavian and the former Soviet Union in Switzerland 1991 and for Romanian nationals in the UK is Eurostat. For the UK the stock in 1989 has been used; extrapolation before 1989.

Table 2 – *Policy dummy variables*

Variable [name in regression table]	Description	Year(s)	Source
Revision of the Aliens Act of 1983 in Denmark [Revision_Den]	Revision of the Aliens Act in October 1986 made it possible to refuse asylum seekers from 'safe countries'.	1987	ICMPD (1994)
Refugees from Sri Lanka and Iran in Norway [RefAsia_Nor]	Many Asian refugees arrived in 1987. This led to policy changes, which were implemented from 1988 on.	1987	ICMPD (1994)
Asyl- and Fremdengesetz in Austria [Fremdeng_Aut]	Austrian authorities significantly tightened asylum law and its enforcement in 1992.	1992	ICMPD (1994)
Asylum system more efficient in Switzerland [AsylumSys_Swi]	Measures to make the system more efficient caused a drastic decrease in asylum applications in 1992.	1992	ICMPD (1994)
Refugees from former Yugoslavia in Sweden [RefYug_Swe]	Many Yugoslav refugees arrived in 1992. Sweden introduced visas for Yugoslav nationals in 1993. ¹	1992	OECD (1998)
Visas for Bosnians in Sweden, effect in Norway [VisaYug_Nor]	Introduction of visas in Sweden in 1993 led to an increase in Norway, which introduced visas in October 1993.	1993	OECD (1998)
Asylum compromise in Germany, effect in the Netherlands [AsylumCom_Net]	The asylum compromise of May 1993 in Germany caused an increase in the number of asylum applications.	1994	Van Wissen and De Beer (2000)
New Aliens Act in the Netherlands [NewAliensAct_Net]	Introduction of the new Aliens Act in 2001. It was expected that the Netherlands would be less attractive by a shorter asylum procedure.	2002-2005	Wijkhuijs et al. (2011)
Amendments to the Aliens Act in Denmark [AmendmentsAA_Den]	The new liberal-conservative government, elected in 2001, headed for stricter asylum policies.	2002-2005	Brekke (2004)

Notes: ¹ This does not apply to Croatian and Slovenian nationals.

All Northern and Western European countries that received considerable numbers of asylum seekers introduced more restrictive asylum procedures in the first half of the 1990s. Belgium, Denmark, France, Germany, Norway, Sweden and the UK introduced these more restrictive asylum procedures in 1993 or in the beginning of 1994 (ICMPD, 1994; OECD, 1998; Angenendt, 1999a, 1999b).

Austria and Switzerland already tightened up their asylum legislation in 1992. Therefore, we expect that the policy dummy variables for Austria and Switzerland would have a negative impact on the share of asylum seekers that these countries attracted in 1992. The Netherlands, on the contrary, did not develop stricter asylum policies until 1994. Hence, the analyses will provide a positive sign for the policy dummy variable for the Netherlands in 1994 in all likelihood. Thus, this policy variable is actually not a reflection of policies in the Netherlands, but of policies in the nearby countries (especially Germany) or a reflection of the lack of stricter asylum policies in the Netherlands in 1993.

Similar to the distribution of asylum seekers over the entire Northern and Western Europe, the distribution of asylum seekers over the Nordic countries can, to some extent, be seen as a system of communicating vessels as well. Halfway the 1980s the number of Asian refugees who sought asylum in the Nordic countries started to increase. The Danish government reacted to this increase with a revision of the Aliens Act of 1983 in October 1986. Therefore, we expect that the dummy variable 'Revision of the Aliens Act of 1983' to have a negative sign. Subsequently, the number of refugees who lodged an asylum application in Norway increased considerably in 1987. A likely cause of this increase is the policy measure in Denmark. Subsequently, Norway took policy measures which have materialised since 1988. Consequently, the dummy variable 'Refugees from Sri Lanka and Iran in 1987' will probably positively affect the share of asylum seekers who lodged an asylum application in Norway. A similar mechanism occurred in the beginning of the 1990s. Instead of Asian refugees, refugees from the former Yugoslavia were the asylum seekers that entered the Nordic countries on a large scale. Again Norway was the country that served as alternative destination after a neighbouring country (in this case Sweden) restricted the possibilities for asylum migration. Many Yugoslavian refugees arrived in Sweden in 1992. The Swedish reaction was the introduction of visas for Yugoslav nationals in 1993. This, in turn, probably led to an increase in the number of Yugoslavian asylum seekers in Norway, which introduced visas for Bosnians in October 1993. We expect the dummy variables 'Refugees from former Yugoslavia in Sweden' and 'Visas for Bosnians in Sweden, effect in Norway' to have positive influences on the share of asylum seekers who lodged an asylum application in Sweden in 1992 and Norway in 1993, respectively.

The asylum policy in Northern and Western European countries gradually changed from policy competition between countries into international policy harmonisation in the second half of the 1990s (Hatton, 2005). Nevertheless, there were two countries - the Netherlands and Denmark - that introduced policy measures which have made these countries less attractive for potential asylum seekers. These two policy measures have become both active in 2001 and probably had an impact on the distribution of the asylum seekers who sought refuge in Northern and Western Europe over the

individual countries in this area from 2002. The Netherlands introduced a new Aliens Act, which should make the country less attractive for asylum seekers because of a shorter asylum procedure (Wijkhuijs *et al.*, 2001). The Danish liberal-conservative government, elected in 2001, introduced a range of restrictive measures that intended to discourage potential asylum seekers to lodge an asylum application in Denmark (Brekke, 2004).

4.3 *Total asylum applications*

The first analysis conducted in this article is an analysis on the distribution of the total number of asylum seekers over all Northern and Western European countries. Table 3 presents the results of this analysis.

Unemployment has a negative significant effect on the share of the total number of asylum seekers in the model presented in table 3. A possible explanation for this finding is that asylum seekers are often seen as competitors at the bottom of the labour market. An increase in unemployment often has a disproportionately large influence on the availability of jobs at the bottom of the labour market (Thurrow, 1975). Even if many (middle) management jobs are downsized, the employment situation at the bottom of the labour market also deteriorates. Displacement of workers with little education by workers with a higher education is the underlying mechanism behind this phenomenon. Therefore, an increase in unemployment may cause public resistance to asylum migration. This resistance can be seen as a determinant of the pressure on authorities to impose (migration) policy measures. Here, restrictions in the admittance policy are the direct causes of changes in the distribution of asylum seekers over the European countries.

It is also possible that economic determinants have a direct impact on the choice of a particular country. This probably holds more for GDP per capita (indicator of facilities for asylum seekers), which has a positive significant effect on the share of the total number of asylum seekers in Northern and Western Europe that a country attracts in the model presented in table 3, than for unemployment (indicator of the probability of obtaining a job). Nevertheless, the possibility of a paid job during the admittance procedure may attract asylum seekers as well.

Contrary to expected, the model reveals a significant negative effect of the migrant stock per capita. A possible explanation for this unexpected finding may be that the population of countries with a large stock of migrants originating from developing their country more often has the feeling that their country reaches the limits of the amount of (lowly skilled) migrants that the country can absorb in economic and social respect. This might result, for instance, in a less positive attitude towards asylum seekers. However, how the matter exactly stands remains largely guesswork. It should be also recorded that the population from Asia, Africa, Latin America, the former Soviet Union, the former

Yugoslavia and Romania is a quite rough proxy for the effects of migrant networks and institutional factors. The migrant stock which originates from a particular sending country of asylum seekers probably is much better indicator of these factors. This induced us to estimate a model for one particular group of asylum seekers, i.e. asylum seekers from the former Yugoslavia (see the next section).

Table 3 – *Parameter estimates of a conditional logit model of the share of the total number of asylum applications in Northern and Western European countries, 1985-2005 (N x T = 252)*

	Coefficients	z-value
Constant ⁱ	-10.54	-
<i>Country-specific dummies</i>		
Austria	1.26 **	3.99
Belgium	1.03 **	6.61
Denmark	0.27	1.16
Finland	-0.58 *	-1.50
France	0.32 *	1.65
Germany	1.37 **	6.79
Irish Republic	-0.17	-0.55
The Netherlands	0.57 **	3.09
Norway	-0.42 *	-1.60
Sweden	1.02 **	7.20
Switzerland	0.78 **	2.70
UK (ref.)	-	-
<i>Policy dummies</i>		
Revision_Den_1987	-0.46	-0.36
RefAsia_Nor_1987	1.11 *	1.47
Fremdeng_Aut_1992	-0.95 *	-1.80
AsylumSys_Swi_1992	-1.06 **	-2.13
VisaYug_Nor_1992	0.52	0.86
RefYug_Swe_1993	0.83 **	3.12
AsylumCom_Net_1994	1.11 **	3.36
NewAliensAct_Net_2002-2005	-0.82 **	-2.68
AmendmentsAA_Den_2002-2005	-0.79 *	-1.42
<i>Socio-economic variables</i>		
GDP per capita / 1000	0.19 **	4.02
Unemployment	-0.14 **	-4.87
Migrant stock per capita	-0.01 **	-2.20

Notes:

ⁱ A constant is not a parameter under the multinomial assumption. Therefore, its z-value is not calculated.

* significant $p < 0.05$ (one-sided test)

** significant $p < 0.01$ (one-sided test)

All policy variables have the sign as expected. Despite two insignificant coefficients, we may state that policy measures have a considerable impact on the distribution of asylum seekers over Northern and Western European countries.

The country-specific dummies are very significant. This means that another underlying mechanism, which is not captured by the variables in the model, has a considerable impact on the distribution of asylum seekers in Northern and Western Europe. For example, the country-specific dummies for Sweden and Germany, which had a reputation of being hospitable and tolerant towards refugees, are larger than average.

4.4 *Asylum applications from the former Yugoslavia*

In this section analyses have been conducted to explain the distribution of asylum seekers from the former Yugoslavia over the most important receiving countries in Northern and Western Europe. Germany, the Netherlands, Sweden, Switzerland and the UK were the most important receiving countries for Yugoslav asylum seekers in absolute terms in the period 1990-2000⁵. We have chosen for asylum applications from the former Yugoslavia as this was the most important country of origin of asylum seekers who sought refuge in Northern and Western Europe in the era that we have studied and for this particular period as the overwhelming majority of the refugees from this former state arrived in Northern and Western Europe in the 1990s and in the year 2000. Table 4 presents the results of a conditional logit model.

The stock of Yugoslav migrants has a significant positive effect on the share of the total number of asylum seekers from the former Yugoslavia that a country attracts in the model presented in table 4. This may be seen as a support for our assumption that the migrant stock which originates from a specific sending country captures a large part of the effects of migrant networks, institutional factors and historical linkages between countries on the distribution of asylum seekers from this country over Northern and Western European states.

The two coefficients of the macro-economic variables in the model have the expected sign. However, both coefficients are not significant. The high correlation between GDP per capita and unemployment may be the cause of this insignificance, because both models with only one macro-economic variable (GDP per capita or unemployment) revealed significant coefficients for these variables.

All policy dummies are significant and have the expected sign. Therefore, we may conclude that asylum policies have a large impact on the dis-

⁵ Actually, Austria belongs to the five most important receiving countries. However, Austria has been kept out of the analyses because of poor data availability.

person of Yugoslavian asylum seekers. This is not very surprising as asylum policies in the 1990s were often a reaction to the large inflow of asylum seekers from the former Yugoslavia.

Table 4 – *Parameter estimates of a conditional logit model of the share of Yugoslav asylum seekers in the five most important receiving countries, 1905-2000 (N x T = 55)*

	Coefficients	z-value
Constant ⁱ	-14.98	-
<i>Country-specific dummies</i>		
Germany	1.57 **	5.29
The Netherlands	0.76 *	1.68
Sweden	2.21 **	6.49
Switzerland	-0.54	-0.31
UK (ref.)	-	-
<i>Policy dummies</i>		
AsylumSys_Swi_1992	-1.14 *	-1.64
RefYug_Swe_1993	1.09 **	3.04
AsylumCom_Net_1994	1.37 **	2.54
<i>Socio-economic variables</i>		
GDP per capita / 1000	0.28	0.75
Unemployment	-0.14	-1.17
Yugoslav migrant stock per capita	0.07 **	2.42

Notes: ⁱ A constant is not a parameter under the multinomial assumption. Therefore, its z-value is not calculated.

* significant $p < 0.05$ (one-sided test)

** significant $p < 0.01$ (one-sided test)

5. CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

The aim of this article was to identify factors that may have an influence on the distribution of asylum seekers in Northern and Western Europe. The possible determinants that were estimated are GDP per capita, unemployment and the migrant stock per capita. Country-specific information was included to control for policy interventions. The analyses consisted of modelling of the distribution of the total number of asylum applications and asylum applications from the former Yugoslavia. The analyses revealed that GDP per capita may have a positive impact and unemployment a negative impact on the share of the asylum seekers who applied for asylum in Northern and Western Europe that a particular country attracts per capita.

All policy variables in the analyses had the expected sign and were, except two, significant. Hence, the conclusion that asylum policies had a

non-negligible impact on the distribution of the asylum seekers who sought refuge in Northern and Western Europe over the individual countries in this area in the period from 1985 to 2005.

Next to macro-economic developments and policy, migrant networks and institutional factors may affect the distribution of asylum seekers. We sought to capture these potential determinants by including the migrant population from Asia, Africa, Latin America, the former Soviet Union, the former Yugoslavia and Romania as an independent variable in our analysis on the total number of asylum seekers. This did not appear to be successful. The migrant stock from these countries even had a negative effect on the distribution of the total number of asylum seeker in this model. However, we did find a positive significant effect of the migrant stock on the distribution of asylum seekers over individual countries when we concentrated the analysis on one specific group of asylum seekers, i.e. those from the former Yugoslavia. In this analysis we used the migrant stock from the former Yugoslavia as independent variable instead of the broad migrant population mentioned above.

We have to be aware of three rather confounding data issues when conducting research into asylum applications. First, pre-selection may be a serious problem. Some countries may have a stricter admittance policy than others. Second, we have to deal with the problem of double counts in the case of lodging an appeal. Finally, some countries only register the main applicant and ignore their children. These confounding data issues may affect the results of our analyses.

It remains to be seen to what extent research into determinants of the distribution of asylum seekers in Northern and Western Europe covers comprehensively the impact of these determinants on asylum migration. It is not inconceivable that determinants in European countries also have an impact on the number of asylum seekers who prefer Europe above other receiving areas (i.e. surrounding countries, North America or Oceania). We may call the latter phenomenon the generation of asylum seekers, while the changing distribution of asylum seekers over European countries may be called the substitution of asylum seekers. Van Wissen and Jennissen (2008) and De Beer (2011) developed methods for inferring substitution and generation from the total number of asylum applications.

As implied in the introduction of this article, we expected that the extension of the EU in eastern direction and the financial-economic crises could have considerably changed the distribution of asylum seekers over the Northern and Western European countries. The EU-membership of former communist countries in Central and Eastern Europe in 2004 has involved that these countries have become subscripts of the so-called Dublin Regulation. This might undermine the transit function of these countries in the asylum flow to Western Europe, as potential asylum seekers who travel through these

countries should lodge an asylum application in these countries themselves. In turn, this could mean a decrease in the share in the total asylum flow to Western Europe of countries like Germany and Austria under conditions of *ceteris paribus*. The financial-economic crises had a relatively larger impact on the Southern European countries than on the Northern and Western European countries and might have also had a negative impact on the job opportunities for illegal migrants in these countries. As already has been mentioned in the first section of this article, it is far from inconceivable that the position of Southern Europe in the European asylum system has been gradually changed from an alternative in the form of illegal labour migration for asylum migration in Northern and Western Europe to the position of a transit area. This could have led to an increase in the share in the total asylum flow to Western Europe of the countries that share a border with Italy and Spain, i.e. France, Switzerland and Austria. These two developments – the extension of the EU in eastern direction and the financial-economic crisis – induced us to limit the period of our research to the year 2005. The existence of the Dublin Regulation plays an important part in the assumption that these two developments have an influence on the distribution of asylum seekers over Northern and Western European countries. However, in the contemporary era with many refugees arriving on the edges of the EU, the governments of the EU- and EFTA-countries have showed that the Dublin Regulation has little meaning in practice. In 2015, this is illustrated by many migrants often travelling through a couple of other EU-countries before they lodge an asylum application in another EU-country, especially Germany. In summary, the distribution mechanisms of asylum seekers over Northern and Western European countries have perhaps changed less than one would expect in the last ten years.

References

- ANGENENDT S. (1999a), “Asylum and migration in the EU member states: Structures, challenges and policies in comparative perspective”. In ANGENENDT S. (ed.), *Asylum and migration policies in the European Union*, Bonn, Europa Union Verlag: 6-64.
- ANGENENDT S. (1999b), “Germany”. In ANGENENDT S. (ed.), *Asylum and migration policies in the European Union*, Bonn, Europa Union Verlag: 166-192.
- BREKKE J.P. (2004), *The struggle for control: The impact of national control policies on the arrival of asylum seekers to Scandinavia 1999-2004*, Oslo, Institute for Social Research.

- CANGIANO A. (2008), "Foreign migrants in Southern European countries: Evaluation of recent data". In RAYMER J., WILLEKENS F.J. (eds.), *International migration in Europe: Data, models and estimates*, Chichester, Wiley and Sons: 89-114.
- CASTLES S., LOUGHNA S. (2003), *Trends in asylum migration to industrialized countries: 1990-2001*, Helsinki, UNU/WIDER.
- CHOTKOWSKI M., SPRANGERS A., NICOLAAS H., BOERSEMA E., DE WINTER J., JENNISSSEN R. (2014), "Asielmigratie". In JENNISSSEN R., NICOLAAS H. (eds.), *De Nederlandse Migratiekaart 2013: Achtergronden en ontwikkelingen in internationale migratiestromen in de periode vanaf 2000*, The Hague, WODC: 129-176.
- DE BEER J.A.A. (2011), *Transparency in population forecasting: Methods for fitting and projecting fertility, mortality and migration*, Groningen, Rijksuniversiteit Groningen.
- ESVELDT I., KULU-GLASGOW I., SCHOORL J.J., VAN SOLINGE H. (1995), *Migratiemotieven, migratienetwerken en partnerkeuze van Turken en Marokkanen in Nederland*, The Hague, NIDI.
- FIJALKOVSKI J. (1993), "Aggressive nationalism, the problem of immigration pressure and asylum policy disputes in today's Germany", *International Migration Review*, 27(4): 850-869.
- HATTON T.J. 2004, "Seeking Asylum in Europe", *Economic Policy*, 19(38): 5-62.
- HATTON T.J. (2005), "European Asylum Policy", *National Institute Economic Review*, 194(1): 106-119.
- HAVINGA T., BÖCKER A. (1999), "Country of asylum by choice or by chance: Asylum seekers in Belgium, the Netherlands and the UK", *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 25(1): 43-61.
- INTERNATIONAL CENTRE FOR MIGRATION POLICY DEVELOPMENT (1994), *The key to Europe: A comparative analysis of entry and asylum policies in Western countries*, Stockholm, Swedish Ministry of Culture.
- KURTHEN H. (1995), "Germany at the crossroads: National identity and the challenges of immigration", *International Migration Review*, 29(4): 914-938.
- MAROUKIS T. 2013, "Economic crisis and migrants' employment: A view from Greece in comparative perspective", *Policy Studies*, 34(2): 221-237.
- MASSEY D.S., ARANGO J., HUGO G., KOUAOUCCI A., PELLEGRINO A., TAYLOR J.E. (1993), "Theories of international migration: A review and appraisal", *Population and Development Review*, 19(3): 431-466.

- MUUS P.J., VAN DAM E.W. (1998), *Comparative research on international migration and international migration policy: Migration from the Maghreb and Turkey to the European Union, and from Mexico, Guatemala and El Salvador to the United States*, Luxemburg: Office for Official Publications of the European Communities.
- NEUMAYER E. (2004), "Asylum destination choice: What makes some West European countries more attractive than others?", *European Union Politics*, 5(2): 155-180.
- NICOLAAS H. (1997), "Daling van het aantal asiolverzoeken zet door in 1996", *Maandstatistiek van de Bevolking*, 45(6): 12-18.
- OECD (1998), *Trends in international migration*, Paris, OECD.
- REYNERI E. (2001), *Migrants' involvement in irregular employment in the Mediterranean countries of the European Union*, Milan, University of Milan Bicocca.
- TE BRAKE A.TH.J. (1993), *Buitenlanders in Oostenrijk*, The Hague, Ministry of Foreign Affairs.
- THIELEMANN E.R. (2003), *Does policy matter? On governments' attempts to control unwanted migration*, San Diego, CCIS.
- THUROW L.C. (1975), *Generating Inequality: Mechanisms of Distribution in the U.S. Economy*, New York, Basic Books.
- TRIANDAFYLIDOU A., MAROUKIS T. (2012), *Migrant smuggling: Irregular migration from Asia and Africa to Europe*, London, Palgrave Macmillan.
- UNHCR (1998), *Asylum in Europe: Arrivals, stay and gender from a data perspective*, Geneva, UNHCR.
- UNITED NATIONS (1997), *International migration and Development: The concise report*, New York, United Nations.
- VAN DAM E., VAN DER ERF R.F. (1998), *Asylum-seekers and refugees, a statistical report. Volume 3: Central European countries*, Luxemburg, Eurostat.
- VAN SELM-THORBURN J. (1998), "Asylum in the Amsterdam Treaty: A harmonious future?", *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 24(4): 627-638.
- VAN WISSEN L.J.G., DE BEER J. (2000), "Internationale migratie in Nederland: Trends, achtergronden, motieven en vooruitzichten". In VAN NIMWEGEN N., BEETS G.C.N. (eds.), *Bevolkingsvraagstukken in Nederland anno 2000*, The Hague, NIDI.
- VAN WISSEN L.J.G., JENNISSEN R.P.W. (2008), "A simple method for inferring substitution and generation from gross flows. An application using asylum requests in Europe". In RAYMER J., WILLEKENS F.J. (eds.), *International migration in Europe: Data, models and estimates*, Chichester, Wiley and Sons: 235-251.

- WENDT H. (1997), "Zuwanderung und Asyl in Deutschland - vor dem Hintergrund demographischer Entwicklungen", *Zeitschrift für Bevölkerungswissenschaft*, 22(2/3): 319-346.
- WIJKHUIJS V., KROMHOUT M., JENNISSEN R. P. W., WUBSH. (2011), "Asielzoekers". In JENNISSEN R. P. W. (ed.), *De Nederlandse migratiekaart: Achtergronden en ontwikkelingen van verschillende internationale migratietypen*. The Hague, BJu: 177-250.
- ZOLBERG A. R., SUHRKE A., AGUAYO S. (1989), *Escape from violence: Conflict and the refugee crisis in the developing world*, Oxford, Oxford University Press.